

1 THE LARGE AND CENTRAL *Caligo martia* EYESPOT MAY REDUCE FATAL ATTACKS BY BIRDS: A
2 CASE STUDY SUPPORTS THE DEFLECTION HYPOTHESIS IN NATURE

3

4 Running title: *Caligo martia* eyespots support the deflection hypothesis.

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27 whose passion for the evolution of butterfly-bird interactions took the field into new heights.

28

29

30

31 **Abstract**

32 Many animals have colorations that resemble eyes, but the functions of such eyespots are debated. *Caligo*
33 *martia* (Godart, 1824) butterflies have large ventral hind wing eyespots, and we aimed to test whether these
34 eyespots act to deflect or to thwart bird attacks through intimidation in a natural community in a *Restinga* Forest
35 in austral South America. We used four types of paper facsimiles: unmanipulated *C. martia* (with eyespots,
36 WE), facsimiles with UV enhanced eyespots (UV), camouflaged facsimiles lacking eyespots (CM), and light-
37 coloured facsimiles that were not camouflaged and lacked eyespots (NC). Two experiments were performed:
38 Experiment 1 used facsimiles in a natural resting position, and in Experiment 2 facsimiles were positioned with
39 the wings open, with ventral wing surfaces and body exposed to viewers. In both experiments facsimiles were
40 placed in two forest sites, organized in 50 blocks with four facsimiles each, and checked for predator attacks
41 every 24 h for five consecutive days. While WE and UV facsimiles were mostly attacked in non-vital areas
42 (wings), most bird attacks on CM were directed at vital body areas. Notably, CM facsimiles had lower attack
43 probability than WE, UV and NC. Our results indicate that *C. martia* eyespots appear to have a deflection
44 function. Eyespots did not appear to reduce attack rates, suggesting that local bird species were not intimidated.
45 Both eyespots and camouflage can be considered efficient functional traits in defence against predation in forest
46 environments, and experiments focusing on local predators and prey are key to our understanding of wing
47 pattern evolution in Lepidoptera.

48

49 **Keywords:** Butterfly facsimiles, Defence strategy, Eye-mimicry, Intimidation, Neotropics, *Restinga* Forest

50

51 **Introduction**

52 Many animal species use eyespots as a defence against predators, and they have evolved independently
53 in various groups of insects, such as Lepidoptera, Hemiptera, Coleoptera and Orthoptera (Stevens, 2005).
54 Butterfly eyespots are characterised by a roughly circular pattern on the wing, with at least two concentric rings
55 or with a single colour disc and a central pupil (Monteiro, 2008) imitating a natural vertebrate eye (Blut et al.,
56 2012; Mukherjee & Kodandaramaiah, 2015) that can be detected by birds. As eye contact is expected to have a
57 strong impact in determining an attack in vertebrate predators, eyespots are considered an important functional
58 trait in the anti-predator strategies of diurnal insects (Shih et al., 2019), being also characterised as ‘eye-
59 mimicry’ (Olofsson et al., 2010). Mimicry is defined as a convergent resemblance of one species to another (or
60 part of another, such as eyes), and this resemblance may encompass morphology, chemistry, sounds, and
61 behaviour (see Quicke (2017) for a review), all of which are important within the context of predator-prey
62 interactions (Endler, 1978; Pinheiro et al., 2016). Mimicry involves at least three groups of organisms: models,
63 mimics, and operators, where models are the organisms that have their characteristics imitated by mimics, and
64 the operators are potential predators that receive the signal emitted by the first two (Endler, 1981). From the
65 perspective of predator-prey interactions, the main difference between crypsis and eye-mimicry is that in the
66 first the operator does not detect the potential prey and thus does not make any decision, while in the case of
67 eye-mimicry, the operator is deceived (Endler, 1981). In some cases both responses by the predator may be
68 acting together (Sargent, 1978).

69 Nymphalid butterflies, especially those in the subfamily Satyrinae, often have eyespots on their wings,
70 which possibly evolved 85-90 million years ago (Oliver et al., 2014). The Nymphalidae Ground Plan describes
71 eyespots as a part of the “border ocelli system” (Nijhout, 1990, 2001), and they may be modified or lost
72 individually in different species. This allows for a wide diversity of patterns, as well as the ability to evolve
73 various types of camouflage or mimicry with precision (Nijhout, 1994). Indeed, the role of eyespots as an anti-
74 predator defence is well documented in Lepidoptera (see Stevens (2005) for a review). Two hypotheses have
75 been proposed (Blest, 1957; Poulton, 1890): (i) deflection, in which the eyespots would serve as “targets” to
76 deflect the attack of predators to a non-vital region of the body, and (ii) intimidation, in which the eyespots
77 would startle predators in an attempt to avoid an attack.

78 Several experimental studies have investigated the role of eyespots in predator-prey interactions,
79 demonstrating that their function may vary depending on the species. Examples of butterfly species where
80 eyespots seem to deflect predator attacks from the body include the Neotropical *Junonia evarete* (Cramer, 1779)

81 (Pinheiro et al., 2014) (Nymphalidae, Nymphalinae), Eurasian *Lopinga achine* (Scopoli, 1763) (Olofsson et al.,
82 2010), and Afrotropical *Bicyclus anynana* (Butler, 1879) (Prudic et al., 2015) (both Nymphalidae, Satyrinae).
83 On the other hand, some works indicate that the number and size of eyespots may intimidate potential avian
84 predators (Ho et al., 2015; Merilaita & Stevens, 2011; Olofsson et al., 2015). In a controlled experiment, models
85 of the Neotropical *Caligo martia* (Godart, 1824) (Nymphalidae, Satyrinae) with intact and disfigured eyespots
86 were presented on a computer monitor with the wings open (exposing the ventral surface) to European great tits
87 (*Parus major*, Paridae), which preferably avoided images with intact eyespots (De Bona et al., 2015). This
88 example is particularly important in the context of our work, which examines the reaction of natural predators to
89 the same butterfly species used by De Bona et al. (2015).

90 Moths in the genus *Catocala* (Noctuidae) have cryptic forewings with conspicuous hindwings that are
91 exposed when the insect is disturbed at rest (Sargent, 1978), evidencing a startle device (deimatic display)
92 (Sargent, 1973; Schlenoff, 1985). It is noteworthy that the deimatic display may occur as a secondary defence
93 strategy against small birds in species that lack typical eyespots, such as *Papilio machaon* Linnaeus, 1758
94 (Papilionidae) (Olofsson et al., 2012), or in butterflies showing deflection marks such as the conspicuous white
95 marginal patches in the hindwing, such as species of *Pierella* (Nymphalidae, Satyrinae) (Hill & Vaca, 2004).
96 Although *Catocala* species constitute classic examples of the intimidation function of hindwing colour patterns
97 (Sargent, 1978), there is limited evidence that butterfly eyespots intimidate potential predators (see Vallin et al.
98 (2007)). Finally, in addition to functioning in predator-prey interactions, butterfly eyespots have also been
99 demonstrated to play a role in courtship behaviour and are thus potentially influenced simultaneously by natural
100 and sexual selection (Crees et al., 2021; Huq et al., 2019; Lyytinen et al., 2003; Oliver et al., 2009; Robertson &
101 Monteiro, 2005). Thus, it is important to evaluate natural avian predator responses when confronting eyespots to
102 properly assess the function of these structures in butterfly-predator interactions. The two mechanisms
103 (intimidation and deflection) may be acting together, being not mutually exclusive, because different bird
104 species may react differently to eyespots depending on the size of the bird or its experience (Vallin et al., 2007).

105 Species of the genus *Caligo* (Nymphalidae, Satyrinae, Brassolini) live in the understory of Neotropical
106 forests and have crepuscular habits (DeVries, 1987). All *Caligo* species have a large, centralised eyespot on the
107 hindwing ventral surface (Crees et al., 2021; Penz & Mohammadi, 2013) that resembles a vertebrate species'
108 eye (De Bona et al., 2015; Stevens, 2005). These butterflies are known to forage and rest on the side of tree
109 trunks during the day. Their eyespots are quite visible against the grey and brown shades of the wing surface,
110 which usually match the background (CAI, pers. obs.) and can thus be considered a form of camouflage. To our

111 knowledge, no experimental study has attempted to evaluate how local predators respond to *Caligo* eyespots.
112 Given their size and conspicuousness, are they intimidating to potential predators? Or do they function as targets
113 that draw predator attacks away from vital areas of the body?

114 Accordingly, we aimed to assess whether the ventral eyespots of *Caligo martia* (Godart, 1824) function
115 as predicted by the intimidation and/or deflection hypotheses. To do so, we performed two field experiments
116 with paper butterfly facsimiles (Figure 1): (i) with eyespots, (ii) with eyespots enhanced with UV ink, (iii) a
117 camouflaged facsimile lacking eyespots and (iv) facsimiles with light wing coloration and lacking eyespots. In
118 the first experiment facsimiles were placed in *C. martia* natural day-resting position, allowing us to compare
119 predator attacks on different types of facsimiles. Under the intimidation hypothesis only, we would predict that
120 facsimiles with eyespots (i and ii) would startle predators and thus be avoided, while those lacking eyespots
121 would be attacked (iii and iv). In contrast, if the deflection hypothesis applies exclusively, we would predict that
122 predators would use eyespots as “targets” of attack (i and ii) and facsimiles lacking eyespots (iii and iv) would
123 sustain fewer beak marks from predators. To complement the first experiment, in the second experiment we
124 used the four facsimiles with the full ventral surface exposed and quantified predation attempts on the wings or
125 body of different facsimile types. Again, the intimidation hypothesis only would lead to a prediction that
126 facsimiles lacking eyespots would show a larger number of predation attempts, and that they would be
127 preferably attacked on the body (thus enhancing probability of prey capture) than on the wings. If only the
128 deflection hypothesis were at play, the opposite would be predicted; that is, facsimiles with eyespot “targets”
129 would show a larger number of beak marks, and be more frequently attacked on the wings than the body. As is
130 often the case in studies performed in the field, the results of our experiments were more complex than the
131 predictions outlined above, underscoring the intricacies of nature. Thus, we discuss our findings within the
132 context of the intimidation and deflection hypotheses alone, and also consider the possibility that both could be
133 at play. Finally, we discuss how local predators responded to wing background colour of facsimiles that lacked
134 eyespots.

135

136 **Material and methods**

137 **Study area**

138 Our study was carried out in two areas of *Restinga* Forest in the Southern Coastal Plain of Rio Grande
139 do Sul, municipality of Capão do Leão: (1) the Horto Botânico Irmão Teodoro Luís (31°48'58" S; 52°25'55"
140 W), and (2) an adjacent area (31°48'54.9" S; 52°25'42.1" W), approximately 300 meters apart. The climate is

141 humid subtropical with hot summers and four well-defined seasons, according to Köppen's classification
142 (Kottek et al. 2006). The annual means of temperature and relative humidity for the region are 17.8 °C and
143 80.7%, respectively, with precipitation of ca. 1366 mm per year (EMBRAPA, 2010). The *Restinga* Forest
144 environments in southern Brazil consist of vegetation patches over sandy deposits, commonly composed of a
145 high density of short plants (up to 12 meters) with emerging tree species, and where three strata can be
146 identified: arboreal, shrubby, and herbaceous (Scherer et al., 2009), forming a well-structured forested
147 environment. This region is part of the Pampa Biome, with vegetation characterized as Pioneer Formations and
148 influenced by the Atlantic Forest (IBGE, 2012). Insectivorous birds present in the area that are large enough to
149 prey on *C. martia* include *Tolmomyias sulphurescens* (Hartert & Goodson, 1917) (14-15 g), *Myiarchus*
150 *swainsoni* Cabanis & Heine, 1859 (21-29 g), *Pitangus sulphuratus* (Linnaeus, 1766) (53-71 g), *Myiodynastes*
151 *maculatus* (Statius Muller, 1776) (43 g), *Tyrannus melancholicus* Vieillot, 1819 (39 g), *Tyrannus savana*
152 Daudin, 1802 (28-32 g), *Empidonomus varius* (Vieillot, 1818) (25 g), *Lathrotriccus eulerei* (Cabanis, 1868) (10-
153 11 g) (all in the family Tyrannidae), and *Trogon surrucura* Vieillot, 1817 (56-78 g) (Trogonidae) (Rafael
154 Antunes Dias, pers. obs.; note variation in body mass in grams (g)).

155 **Sampling design**

156 We used natural-size, facsimile models of *C. martia* (facsimiles hereafter) with eyespot about 1 cm in
157 diameter. This butterfly is common in the Restinga Forest region (Gallo, 2018). The software Adobe Photoshop®
158 was used to manipulate collection specimen photographs and produce four colour morphs: (i) with unmanipulated
159 eyespots (WE, Figure 1a); (ii) with the lighter ring of the eyespots enhanced with ultraviolet ink (UV, Figure 1b
160 and Supplementary Information Figure S1); (iii) without eyespots, corresponding to camouflage (CM, Figure 1c);
161 and (iv) without eyespots and with lighter coloration, not camouflaged (NC, Figure 1d). All facsimiles were laser-
162 printed on white sulfite paper and hand-cut. To visualize marks produced by predators, a thin layer of Acrilex
163 modelling clay (black 520™) was placed on all *Caligo* facsimiles as described below. Experimental facsimiles
164 were attached to tree trunks with wood glue (Figure 2).

165

166

167 Figure 1: Facsimiles used in the experiments: a) with original eyespots (WE); b) eyespots enhanced with
 168 ultraviolet ink (UV); c) eyespots removed, original background colour (CM); d) eyespots removed, lighter
 169 background colour (NC).

170

171 The study included two experiments carried out between March and June 2019. Each experiment was
 172 composed of 50 blocks that included the four different facsimiles (a total of 200 facsimiles per experiment). The
 173 four facsimiles were randomly placed, and at least 30 cm apart from each other within individual trees (Howe et
 174 al., 2009) (Figure 2). Although *Caligo* butterflies do not naturally aggregate when resting during the day,
 175 grouping the four facsimiles would potentially attract the attention of foraging birds, thus increasing the chance
 176 that our facsimiles would be sampled, as the predators could visualise all facsimiles before selecting one for
 177 predation (Barnett et al., 2016). Sample blocks were set 20 meters apart and along a linear transect inside the
 178 two study sites, covering approximately 30 hectares. Facsimiles remained in the field during five consecutive
 179 days, and predation attempts were recorded at 24 h, 48 h, 72 h, 96 h and 120 h (Barnett et al., 2016). The clay of
 180 every attacked facsimile was remodelled in the field as necessary to remove beak marks before the next day of
 181 sampling. If the attack destroyed a facsimile including not only the clay but the paper too, we replaced it with an
 182 equivalent one to complete the sampling period. The total sampling effort was 1000 observations during the
 183 five-day sampling period.

184

185 Figure 2: Arrangement of facsimiles within a block under the distinct experiments. A) Experiment 1 and B)

186 Experiment 2.

187

188 In the first experiment, facsimiles were placed to resemble the natural day-resting position of a *Caligo*

189 butterfly (Figure 2A), and modelling clay was laid on the border of the wings (see photos in Figure 3). The

190 exclusion of the body in the first experiment allowed us to focus exclusively on the effect of eyespots (or lack

191 thereof) in a standardised manner by limiting predators' choice/potential attacks to the wings themselves. As

192 such, the analyses related to the first experiment focused on the beak marks left by bird predators on the wings

193 of the facsimiles, which in most cases occurred near and/or at the eyespot location. In the second experiment,

194 the facsimiles included a body and were presented with the full ventral surface exposed so that potential

195 predators could view all four wings (Figure 2B). In this case, the birds would be able to attack the body of these

196 facsimiles just as easily as they would the wings, thus complementing the first experiment. Modelling clay was

197 placed on the border of the wings and on the body, which allowed us to compare the predator attacks on

198 different body parts, *i.e.*, wings or body. Despite the un-natural position of *Caligo* in our second experiment, it

199 was an efficient way to expose the body fully to a potential predator attack. Finally, we also note that an

200 ongoing experiment at the same *Restinga* forest with another facsimile butterfly with several marginal eyespots

201 on the wings (a small-brown Satyrini) suggests that local birds do not direct their attack to the butterfly head or
202 body (after 1000 observations, only two attacks were made on the body, CAI unpublished data).

203 In both experiments, our response variable was attacks by birds, recorded as absence or presence of
204 distinct “V-shaped” beak marks, which varied in size and/or shape depending on the bird, made by predators
205 regardless of the number of marks on a facsimile (Saporito et al., 2007) (Figure 3). Each time the facsimiles
206 were checked in the field, beak marks were removed by reshaping the modelling clay. This allowed us to use the
207 same facsimiles for five consecutive days, and to account for repeated predation events (see Brodie (1993) for
208 additional details).

209

210

211 Figure 3: Beak marks (indicated by the red arrows) on the modelling clay placed on the facsimiles of *Caligo*
212 *martia* butterflies. A) beak mark near the facsimile with original eyespot in the Experiment 1; B) beak mark in
213 the facsimile without eyespot (camouflage) in Experiment 2; C) beak mark in the facsimile without eyespots and
214 with lighter coloration in Experiment 2.

215

216 **Data analysis**

217 In the first experiment, to assess the effect of butterfly colour pattern on the occurrence of predation,
218 we fitted generalised linear mixed models (GLMM). The response variable followed a binomial distribution
219 (i.e., presence or absence of beak marks), with a complementary clog-log link, to reduce any asymmetrical 0-1
220 values in the samples (Zuur et al., 2009); see Supplementary Information (Figure S2) for a schematic
221 representation of the study. In order to achieve the principle of independence between variables, we considered
222 each block as a random effect in GLMMs. In the second experiment, to obtain the predation probability per
223 facsimile, we fitted GLMMs (binomial distribution, logit link, block as random effect) for each facsimile. All

224 analyses were conducted in the R environment for statistical computing (R Core Team, 2023), by using
225 functions from lme4 and MuMIn packages (Bartón, 2020; Bates et al., 2022).

226

227 **Results**

228 Considering both experiments combined, we observed a higher number of beak marks on facsimiles
229 that had eyespots (WE plus UV, N = 80) than on facsimiles that lacked eyespots (CM plus NC, N = 53) (Table
230 1). Nonetheless, each of our experiments uncovered different aspects of the predator responses to the facsimiles.

231 In the first experiment, we registered a total of 94 beak marks on the wings (Table 1). Camouflaged
232 facsimiles (CM) showed the lowest number of beak marks while the light-coloured facsimiles that were not
233 camouflaged (NC) had the highest. The two facsimiles with eyespots (WE and UV) had a similar number of
234 attacks by birds and incurred an almost identical attack rate as NC. The calculated predation probabilities
235 through GLMM statistically categorise the facsimiles as $CM < WE = UV = NC$ (Figure 4, Table 2).

236

237 Table 1: Number of beak marks recorded for each facsimile in Experiment 1 (E1) and Experiment 2 (E2).

238 Abbreviations: WE, facsimile with original eyespots; UV, eyespots enhanced with ultraviolet ink; CM, eyespots
239 removed, original background color; NC, lighter background color.

240

Facsimile	E1	E2			Grand Total
		Body	Wing	Total	
WE	27	4	11	15	42
UV	27	4	7	11	38
CM	11	2	1	3	14
NC	29	7	3	10	39
Grand Total	94	17	22	39	133

241

242

243 Table 2: Results of the fixed effects of the generalised linear mixed model (GLMM) that evaluated the
 244 differences in the probability of predation among four different butterfly facsimiles in Experiment 1 (E1) and
 245 Experiment 2 (E2). The explained variance for fixed (R2m) and fixed + random (R2c) effects is also shown. SE
 246 = standard error; WE = facsimiles with unmanipulated eyespots; UV = facsimiles with eyespot lighter ring
 247 enhanced with ultraviolet ink; CM = facsimiles without eyespots and unmanipulated background colour
 248 (camouflaged); and NC = facsimiles without eyespots and with lighter background coloration (not
 249 camouflaged). Note that for Experiment 2 all the results shown are the ratio of attacks on wings in relation to the
 250 body.
 251

Experiment 1

Facsimile	Estimate	SE	z value	p value	R2m	R2c
Intercept: WE	-2.369	0.23	-10.19	< 2e-16	0.07	0.28
Facsimile CM	-0.956	0.35	-2.661	0.007		
Facsimile UV	-0.002	0.27	-0.007	0.994		
Facsimile NC	0.064	0.27	0.24	0.81		

Experiment 2

Facsimile	Estimate	SE	z value	p value	R2m	R2c
NC:wing	-5.9	2.5	-2.3	0.02	0.003	0.9
CM:wing	-0.7	1.2	-0.5	0.5	0.003	0.003
WE:wing	3.5	1.8	1.9	0.05	0.03	0.96
UV:wing	2.2	1.5	1.4	0.14	0.01	0.9

252

253

254 Figure 4: Predation probabilities for the four facsimiles in Experiment 1. Black horizontal lines indicate the
 255 median estimated values, the box shows the 25th and 75th percentiles, and the black points represent outlier
 256 values. Abbreviations: WE, facsimile with original eyespots; UV, eyespots enhanced with ultraviolet ink; CM,
 257 eyespots removed, original background colour; NC, lighter background colour.

258

259 In the second experiment we analysed potential trends and differences in predation between wings and
 260 body (Table 1, Figure 5a and Figure 5b). Among the four facsimiles, WE and NC showed the most distinct
 261 predation patterns between wings and body. While WE facsimiles had a higher proportion of beak marks on
 262 their wings, NC had a higher predation probability on the body (Figure 5a, Figure 5b i and iv, Table 2). Both
 263 WE and UV facsimiles showed a higher proportion of beak marks on the wings than on the body, and the
 264 reverse was the case for facsimiles that lacked eyespots. Similar to the first experiment, fewer beak marks were
 265 observed on the CM facsimiles (Figure 5a), and despite the few bird attacks, the trend for this facsimile fits that
 266 of NC, that is, a higher number of attacks on the body than on the wings (Figure 5, Figure 5b iv). Furthermore,
 267 this experiment showed that the facsimile that best matched the real appearance of *C. martia* (WE) showed the
 268 highest number of beak marks (wing and body combined; Table 1, Figure 5b i), and also that facsimiles with

269 eyespots were mostly attacked on the wings while those that lacked eyespots were mostly attacked on the body
 270 (Figure 5b iv).
 271

272
 273 Figure 5: Predation probability at wings and body across different *Caligo martia* butterfly facsimiles. a) Number
 274 of attacks on wings (circles) and body (diamonds) for the four facsimiles in Experiment 2. b) Comparisons of
 275 predation probability at wings (W) or body (B) across the facsimiles. Different letters show statistical
 276 differences among the predation probability, while equal letters show no statistical differences. Abbreviations
 277 and figures in panel b: (i) WE, facsimile with original eyespots; (ii) UV, eyespots enhanced with ultraviolet ink;
 278 (iii) CM, eyespots removed, original background colour; (iv) NC, lighter background colour.

279

280 **Discussion**

281 Given their particularly large size and resemblance to vertebrate eyes, we asked whether the ventral
 282 eyespots of *Caligo martia* function as predicted by the intimidation or by the deflection hypotheses. The life-
 283 size facsimiles used in the two complementary experiments were exposed to at least nine species of native
 284 insectivorous birds (see Materials and Methods and Figure 2). Despite the limitations of experiments that use
 285 artificial models, this study is the first empirical test of the defensive function of *Caligo* eyespots in nature,
 286 suggesting that their single, large, central eyespot most likely functions within the context of deflection rather
 287 than intimidation in our studied community.

288 The intimidation hypothesis predicts that eyespots frighten potential predators, thus preventing an
 289 attack (Blest, 1957; Poulton, 1890). To test if vertebrate eye-mimicry intimidated predators, De Bona et al.

290 (2015) used *Caligo martia* images with intact and disfigured eyespots in a controlled experiment. Facsimiles
291 with the wings open (as in our Figure 2b) were presented on a computer monitor to European great tits (*Parus*
292 *major*, Paridae), which preferably avoided images with intact eyespots. Unlike the experimental design by De
293 Bona et al. (2015), which presents a Neotropical butterfly presented to a European bird in the laboratory, our
294 study exposed *C. martia* facsimiles to native predators in the field and our results indicated that local
295 insectivorous birds attacked the large and conspicuous eyespots of the *C. martia* facsimiles. Interestingly, Vallin
296 et al. (2007) observed that the response to eyespot size (and prey size) varied between two *Parus* species of
297 different body sizes. As we did not have direct observations of birds interacting with butterfly facsimiles, we
298 cannot assess whether all bird species present in our study site had the same reaction to *C. martia* eyespots (see
299 Methods for variation in size). Given that this butterfly is very common (CAI, pers. obs.), mature adult birds in
300 our study area likely had prior experience with it. Yet, if they were intimidated by *C. martia* eyespots, we would
301 have expected few beak marks on the facsimiles that most faithfully represented this butterfly species (WE), but
302 this was not the case.

303 The deflection hypothesis predicts that eyespots function as “targets” that drive predator attacks away
304 from vital areas of the prey’s body. Like most species in the tribe Brassolini (Satyrinae), *C. martia* has a large
305 eyespot below hindwing vein CuA1 (Penz & Mohammadi, 2013). This region of the wing (tornus) has been
306 historically recognized as a prime location for predator attacks (Carpenter, 1933, 1937, 1942; Collenette &
307 Talbot, 1928) and it has been demonstrated to tear easily (DeVries, 2002, 2003; Hill & Vaca, 2004). Several
308 studies have provided evidence in support of the deflection hypothesis (Olofsson et al., 2010; Stevens, Stubbins,
309 et al., 2008; Vallin et al., 2011). In the Neotropical region in particular, Pinheiro et al. (2014) showed that birds
310 attacked butterflies’ eyespots through field observation of beak-marks on *Junonia evarete*, and also found a
311 higher frequency of beak-marks on females than males. Furthermore, wing tears involving eyespots were more
312 frequent than expected by chance, which suggests that birds were indeed using eyespots as “targets” for attacks.
313 The results of our Experiment 1 agree with findings of Pinheiro et al. (2014) and the predictions of the
314 deflection hypothesis (see Introduction), given that *C. martia* facsimiles with eyespots had a higher predation
315 probability than the camouflaged facsimile that lacked eyespots. Moreover, in the European region, Olofsson et
316 al. (2010) found that ultraviolet light influenced predators, observing that bird attacks on *Lopinga achine*
317 (Scopoli, 1763) (Nymphalidae) were directed to the marginal eyespots of the wings only in a low UV intensity
318 environment. We did not find an influence of UV reflectance in our study, as facsimiles with eyespots and those
319 with UV-enhanced eyespots were attacked at a similar frequency (Table 1, Figure 4). Although some studies

320 reported the importance of UV light to visual tests performed with birds (Ho et al., 2015; Olofsson et al., 2010),
321 our results showed that UV did not have a primordial function in the decision-making by the local bird predators
322 within the microhabitat where the experiments were performed. It is nonetheless possible that UV light might be
323 important within the context of mate selection (Huq et al., 2019; Robertson & Monteiro, 2005), as are the size
324 and central position of the wing eyespot as suggested by Crees et al. (2021). Finally, although the presence of
325 large eyespots might increase detectability by predators as compared to the camouflaged facsimile, our results
326 show that, once detected, eyespots may deflect the attack away from the body. We note, however, that in
327 Experiment 1 facsimiles did not have modelling clay on the body, which prevents us from comparing bird
328 attacks to the body *vs.* wings in a natural resting position.

329 The two facsimiles that lacked eyespots (Figure 1c, d) were perceived differently by the local birds.
330 Not surprisingly, the camouflaged facsimile with normal *Caligo* wing background colour showed fewer beak
331 marks than the light-coloured facsimile. Camouflage has been widely recognized as an effective means of
332 protection against predation in many animal groups (see Quicke (2017) for a review), and it is likely that our
333 dark-coloured facsimiles lacking eyespots were less noticeable to birds by being similar to the background of
334 the *Restinga* forest interior. Furthermore, predation probabilities were similar for the light-coloured facsimile
335 and each of the facsimiles with eyespots. There are two possible explanations for this finding. First, our light-
336 coloured facsimile showed some resemblance to the white *Morpho epistrophus catenaria* Perry, 1811
337 (Nymphalidae) that coexists with *C. martia* in our area (Gallo 2018) and is commonly attacked by birds (CAI
338 pers. obs.). This *Morpho* species nonetheless has a series of dark eyespots that are likely noticeable to birds.
339 Second, and most likely, the highly visible light-coloured facsimile possibly drew the attention of local
340 predators by being a novel pattern (Benson, 1972).

341 The association between a conspicuous eyespot and a camouflaged background pattern suggests the
342 existence of an optimisation of two defence strategies in the same organism to avoid predation, since there is a
343 chance of damage by predators when the prey attracts their attention (Kang et al., 2017; Stevens, 2005).
344 Nonetheless, losing part of the wings would be less detrimental than having vital parts attacked because, when
345 camouflaged organisms are detected, the attempt of predation can be fatal. In the case of *C. martia*, these two
346 features can promote both defence strategies depending on the distance and detection capacity of predators,
347 potentially increasing survivorship (Stevens, Hardman, et al., 2008). It seems possible that when bird predators
348 come close enough to identify the eyespot and the camouflaged wing pattern is not sufficient, they might indeed
349 direct their attack to the attractive eyespot “target”.

350 We observed less than half as many predator attacks on facsimiles positioned with the wings open
351 (Experiment 2, 39 beak marks) than on facsimiles in normal resting position (Experiment 1, 94 beak marks). We
352 attribute this to the un-natural position of the facsimiles, as the two experiments were performed in the same
353 area and time frame, or to the intimidation to some bird species that may recognise the shape of the facsimiles as
354 a large vertebrate face. According to Vallin et al. (2007), intimidation or deflection depend on the avian
355 predator's size and experience, in which juveniles and small bird species perceive the central and large eyespot
356 as a threat and avoid attempting predation. On the other hand, adult and larger bird species attack the butterflies
357 directly in the eyespot, allowing escape. The studies of Ho et al. (2015) and De Bona et al. (2015) corroborate
358 the results found in Experiment 2, and these findings may demonstrate that both predation-avoidance strategies
359 can work at the same time. Keeping in mind that our study was carried out in nature with artificial butterflies,
360 the results of Experiment 2 nonetheless showed that facsimiles with eyespots were preferentially attacked on the
361 wings, while those lacking eyespots were generally attacked on the body (Figure 5). Even though facsimiles in
362 Experiment 1 did not have a body covered by modelling clay, results from this experiment support the deflective
363 function of *C. martia*'s eyespots. Using chickens as experimental predators, Mukherjee & Kodandaramaiah
364 (2015) found that eyespot "pairedness" decreased the number of attacks on facsimiles of *Junonia almana*
365 (Linnaeus, 1758) (Nymphalidae, Nymphalinae). The discrepancy between their results and those of our
366 Experiment 2 is likely due to differences in the sensory system of the experimental birds. Visually oriented
367 predators have the ability to recognize the shape of their potential prey, underscoring the importance of using
368 local butterfly and predator species in experimental studies. Experiments carried out in nature and accounting
369 for habitat type, environmental conditions (Lyytinen et al., 2003; Stevens, Hardman, et al., 2008), and the
370 availability of natural predators (Pinheiro et al., 2014) are expected to produce more reliable evidence of the use
371 of eyespots as a defence against predation.

372 Most experiments that aim to test the intimidation and deflection hypotheses are performed in
373 controlled conditions, use captive predators that are not always sympatric with the focal butterflies (*e.g.*, great
374 tits, chickens), or use facsimiles that do not resemble living insects. It is, therefore, not surprising that there is no
375 consensus on the influence of eyespot size and number on the effectiveness of anti-predator defence (Ho et al.,
376 2015; Stevens & Ruxton, 2014). Although the deflection hypothesis is usually associated with small and
377 numerous eyespots at the edge of the wing (Ho et al., 2015; Kodandaramaiah, 2011; Stevens, 2005), our results
378 generally supported this hypothesis, even though the ventral eyespots of *C. martia* are large, highly conspicuous,
379 and potentially intimidating (see also Vallin et al. (2007)). We note, however, that the experimental design did

380 not allow us to assess how each individual bird species in our study site reacted to *Caligo* eyespots. When
381 studying potential functions of butterfly eyespots, experimental biologists should avoid making broad
382 generalisations based on narrow sets of conditions. We are aware of a possible bias inherent to the use of
383 artificial facsimiles in nature and recognize limitations of Experiment 1 *a posteriori* (lack of modelling clay on
384 the body). Nonetheless, our experiments highlight the importance of evaluating the role and use of functional
385 traits in nature and focusing on local communities that interact in both ecological and evolutionary time. In this
386 way, we aimed to improve the knowledge of anti-predator strategies as a proxy for a much larger goal: to
387 comprehend the complex interactions that maintain the biodiversity of a megadiverse region such as the
388 Neotropics.

389

390 **Authors' contributions**

391 CAI: Conceptualization; Data curation; Investigation; Funding Acquisition, Supervision; Writing.

392 STM, BBF, and CAC: Conceptualization; Data curation; Investigation; Writing.

393 CMP: Investigation; Writing.

394 TS: Investigation; Writing.

395 KMB: Investigation; Analyses; Writing.

396

397 **Data availability statement**

398 The processed data and R codes used to conduct all analyses are available at

399 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116939>.

400

401 **Conflicts of interest**

402 The authors declare no conflict of interests in this work.

403

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Supplementary Information

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Figure S1: Facsimile with the lighter ring of the eyespots enhanced with ultraviolet light.

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Figure S2: Scheme explaining data analysis, from the main question, dataset, issues, and developed model.

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